

ESSAY ON THE PSYCHOPATHOLOGY OF THE ETHER OF LIVING SPACE

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Abstract: The essay presented here discusses the phenomenon of the appearance of luminous corpuscles in front of the mind and the visual field. In the introduction, we outlined some aspects of an sick humanity. In the following topic, we base ourselves on general lines the concept of ether. And finally, in the last topic, we address the central theme of this essay: the stimulation of the vibration of these particles as they fill the patient's lived space, causing a series of appearances of luminous ghosts. Our method is phenomenological. And our objective is to bring to the reader a certain theorization of a very little known topic in phenomenological psychopathology.

Keywords: Psychopathology. Ether. Living space.

Initial considerations

At the height of the turmoil of the 19th century and between the interstice of two world wars, the mark of the concept of “existence” was embedded in the image of the world. Such an existence, above all, human, made man a “demigod”. In fact, this entire egocentric vision made philosophy a way of survival whose guiding center of the world should always be the *human-being* to the detriment of other beings. Even with the civil, cultural and economic wars of centuries past since Antiquity, it was the 19th century, *man's outcome in the tragedy of himself*. Therefore, for many, its image became “distorted”, its nebulous reflection and so-called “egocentrism” gave rise to the structuring of a human race that had definitely “gone crazy”. Today, this is *the image* that some mystics (or all of them) made themselves out of the mundane man: “a man trapped within himself with deep psychic marks that reveal his fragility and his great perplexity in the face of the reflection he has become”.

This brief historical overview of this essay was just to say that it was, in the 19th century, that abstract and brilliant minds created the ultimate meaning for our existence - a foundation for the clarification of the *illness* of the human race itself - when, in the heat of revolutions, - man *fell ill*. Thus, in our view, even if science in general has made possible the image of man as a “demigod”, on the other hand, man's own reflection when seeing himself in the image of the world

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becomes *corrupted*. Therefore, its physical structure and, above all, *psychic*, ended up dissolving next to the *corruptibility* of the world itself and, even more so, of the *human thinking*.

What is meant here in other words is that, even if the human race did not immediately realize it, but it was necessarily their “thought” or “the image or *collective consciousness* of his own thinking” (JUNG, 2002), the *germ* which unleashed the dark corruptibility of the world, as well as of the entire *psyche* of this current era. That being said, unfortunately the man didn't notice and by the time he woke up, it was too late.

It turns out that it's incredible how human beings live for the sake of living, but, in short, they don't realize the “damage” they are doing to the world and, worst of all, to themselves. And, detail, all this serious *rupture* presented here *crumbles* all worldly buildings; both the human intellect suffers such “corrosion”, as does the living image of the world or, if to speak with a term from Merleau-Ponty (2018), *the flesh of the world*. Thus, it seems that since the 19th century, which would be the beginning of the “boom catastrophic”, the entire structure of our world then decided to dilute itself.

Therefore, it is in this *rehearsal*, which we will demonstrate how the *human psyche* (above all, *the thought*) has an intrinsic relationship with the illness of a large number of beings who, in the end, did not realize it, but they themselves are the main cause of the illness. *rot* of the flesh of the world. However, we remember here that we will not present the universal effects (or of the world), but we will focus on a specific part of this “illness” and this particularity would be a brief “psychopathology of the ether of the lived space”. Again, we remember: the human being does not realize (or pretends not to notice), but his entire psychic structure has been *ruined* due, again, “to the impetration of the opposite movement of *your thinking* in the substantial content of the fabric of space”. Therefore, a few effects of this will be presented here in a kind of *phenomenologization of lived space* in a symptomatically altered (“ill”) psyche whose common thread connecting “mind” and “corporeality” are seen as the product of a little-known but real substance - “the ether”.

2. O ether

But why the “ether”? What would be the relationship between “ether” and psychology (or the psyche)? Being the “ether” raw material of Nature, what does it have to do with humans? The ether, to use a metaphor, would be “a *psychic seed* in a state of germination as it *proliferates* in the space of life” (ROERICH, 1930). On the other hand, the concept of “ether” in physics appears as an “immeasurable” and “unfathomable” invisible point; it would be, physically speaking, “an infinitesimal particle present in the atmosphere which it is possible to feel, but not “see”. It turns out

that, for physics, the “ether” can only “exist” in the presence of *light waves* because without light the ether could not exist. Because it is as if particles of an “etheric” nature were also contained in every focus of luminosity and, furthermore, their “viscosity” character would only be possible with the absolute presence of “light” at the same time. In view of this, each ethereal force *would encourage* centripetally when colliding abruptly with the also sudden *luminosity*. Both the light waves provide strength and give corporeality to the ether particles, and the latter contract and spread thanks to the light waves.

However, for the purposes of this essay, we need to dwell on a single form of the ether that would be - “the ether of space”. In, *Treatise on light*, Huygens (1660) tells us - “the luminous ether *penetrates* the substance of every material body with little or no resistance, as free perhaps as the wind passes through a grove of trees.” In other words, the etheric vehicle *permeates everything* because, moreover, it permeates the entire material body and, moreover, something like “matter” is created from the ether and three other substances - atom, energy and time. However, it turns out that the ether of space has a specificity. As the ether generally accommodates or shapes itself in every material body, before that, it insinuates itself into all the subterranean layers of space. Such space without temporality is nothing because beyond the movement provided by the particles of ether; This set of ethers can only move in space through the dynamics of time. However, space time here will not be our focus.

Said in very synthetic and simplistic terms, space has a spatiality that becomes a “being”. Yes, many physicists to prove what mystics claim have realized that space is a “being”; a being with every possible designation in the etymology of the word. Some philosophers even speak of an “ontology of the being of space”. This definition is given precisely because of the *proof* of the existence of ether in space. The nature of time would give the movement or dynamics of space, while the nature of ether would constitute the “mind” of space and, moreover, this ether would be responsible for “giving body” to space. That is why we speak today of a “lived space” in the science of phenomenological psychopathology precisely because this term is only possible because space, with the ether and its profound etherization, *thinks* how a human thinks. Therefore, in the introduction to this essay, we briefly talk about how humanity has deteriorated, mainly due to its own psyche. In this way, the theory of the ether of space would be one of the keys to understanding the illness of the structures of the experiential world whose effect reflects in all corners of space.

Here, “space” would be the key term. For now, not the “lived space”, but the space *automatically*, that is, “space” in physical terms. Science has already proven substantially and through experiments the existence of the ether. On the other hand, esoteric science is much further ahead when it sees in the “ether of space” a form of *living being*. They think like this - “as everything in the atmosphere is created and at the same time alive, the ether would be, for them, the

primary substance originating from the Cosmos and which *shape* all. The author of this essay, when carrying out a thorough research on the “etherization of space”, found nothing in terms of physics, only in the field of esotericism. As said, physics only proved the existence of the ether, but the “functioning” behind the dynamics of etherization of space, for physicists, is still a mystery, an unknown.

Physicist Huygens (1660) says - “I will say, however, that it can be conceived that these particles of ether, despite their small size, are still composed of other parts, and *its elasticity* consists of the very rapid movement of a *subtle matter*, that the *cross* from all sides, and forces its structure to be arranged in such a way as to provide *this fluid* the most open and easy passage possible.” Modern physics, since Newton, has already proven that the “ether” is a type of *watery liquid* (or a fluid) that permeates and/or passes through every material body. In addition to physics, metaphysics since Aristotle has suggested that the ether is a subtle and/or celestial matter that physicists themselves today say that, without being able to discover its real origin, they just say that it is God's creation and mystery.

Therefore, fluid, electric or magnetic matter, the ether since the philosophers of Egypt and the East (long before Greek Antiquity), appears as a *absolute reality*. After this time, as stated in the introduction, this 19th century was the *momentum* decisive for science, without a doubt, because personalities such as Helena Blavatsky, Rudolf Steiner, Alice Bailey, Helena Roerich, Charles Leadbeater, Annie Besant, among others; During their terrestrial and existential passage, they left deep and very true foundations about the *genesis* and the *operation* of the ether in cosmic space. If during Antiquity it was still a great mystery, since the 19th century and due to the living presence of these beings, the etherealization of the world today is a proven and evident reality.

According to Einstein (1920), the ether appears to be truly an “abstract, self-moving entity at the moment its particles *vibrate* splendidly in the “empty” middle of space – he says – “it seemed indisputable that light should be interpreted as a vibratory process in an inert elastic medium that filled all space.” This light, for Einstein, would be *the luminescence of the vibration process of the etherization of all space*; what Isaac Newton called “luminiferous ether” which in Theosophy with Blavatsky is called “luminous ether”. In this way, both the *obscuration* of space, as to its *lighting* in the fabric of space would be caused by the etherization of ether particles. In esoteric terms, the ether is both Light and Dark.

Every luminous corpuscle is made up of light on the one hand and ether on the other. Einstein in 1920 had already proven that the entire environment contains luminous corpuscles (or vibrating waves of light) and this “medium” is filled by ether which, suddenly and immediately, will constitute the space we know. Thus, the prominence of every material body given and/or seen in space is due to corpuscles made up of “light”, as well as “ether”. Even so, the ether is contained

in both light and space. It turns out that space is also a matter, and a living one, otherwise it would not exist. Being matter, all space is filled with light together with ether because light is already an etheric matter. Thus, the space *absorb* the ethereal light and becomes “luminous”. This is in physical terms.

In mystical terms, space is a “living being” that through light and ether *creates* its existence. Therefore, the space accommodates every surface, this surface being the light. The light would be *the substrate* of space that would “move” it through the ether particles. Once the space is illuminated, the entire material body then appears, absorbing all the remains of the light co-created when the space was constituted. Thus and only thus, matter *acquire* form when before it was also an invisible corpuscle like the ether. Light, atom and ether would form the space we know.

To prove this, in the *Book of spirits*, Allan Kardec ([1897] (2021)) states - “there is an ethereal fluid that *fill* space and *penetrates* the bodies. *This fluid* is the ether or primitive cosmic matter, generator of the world and beings”. Elsewhere, he also says - “God, as Supreme Intelligence, primary cause of all things, Spirit, as Intelligent Being, and matter are the principle of everything that exists, with matter (coagulated light) being a stage transitory of the universal cosmic fluid/ether”.

In summary: physics proves the existence of ether in the medium (space) and metaphysics and/or mysticism describes in depth the process of etherization of its particles.

3. The psychopathology of lived space

Again, we say, only with the scientific progress of the 19th century did the theory about the ether begin to be successful. We say this because, in this century, Minkowski ([1933] (2011)), also a physicist, created a theory about spatiality and, with this, brought a “physical” category that is space to psychopathology. Minkowski was correct. The theory about the lived space is even evident in diagnosing possible psychic changes in the individual, among which the following stand out: “agoraphobia” and “social phobia”, as well as “visual-spatial hallucination” or “space neurosis” . .

In this last topic of our essay, we will deal with two very peculiar cases presented in Vol.1 of *General psychopathology* by Karl Jaspers (1979). These case examples are true and very rich. Let's see:

Case 01

An example of sense memory is the following self-description (from Privy Councilor Tuzek of Marburg, who made it friendly to us): “A large part of the day had occupied me for hours on end in picking apples. On a ladder, he manipulated

the apple picker, looking continuously upwards at the treetops and pulling the scissors tied to a long stick. When I went to the railway station at night through the city's dimly lit streets, *I was significantly hampered on my walk by constantly seeing branches loaded with apples in front of me.* The phenomenon was so insistent that I couldn't help but walk with my cane in front of me, shaking the empty air; the phenomenon lasted several hours until I lay down and fell asleep (JASPERS, 1979, p. 86, emphasis added).

This case is very characteristic of how inert matter in concrete space becomes a *living matter* when transmitted to the mind in the form of a representation within a certain perceptual interval of time. I dealt with this specific state in the essay “The object nothing”². Here, once again, it is the relationship with the lived space that projects and projects things like this to us. Or rather, it teleports us to a state or situation that is often strange and that seems “abnormal” to us. Like this case of the glimpse of apple fire, the same thing can happen to anyone unless they spend minutes or even hours on end in a single visual-spatial direction. The thing is, as Aristotle (2015) said, “life is a mimesis of reality”, that is, if everything is a reflection, what can we say about our mind. Before something moves, the mind beforehand *had already moved*. And this movement is the reflection that she herself makes around her and, above all, within herself. We cannot say that this case is a clear example of psychopathology, but, if it happens recurrently, several times, it can evolve into a condition of *paranoia*.

Tuczek's lived space is the treetop. There is the origin of the recurrent and sudden intuitive optical image of his “visual agony”. Said in an abstract and profound way, in this space, within the apples and among the trees there was in fact a *tuning* of ethereal and atomic energy flowing without cessation. The apples were there; in their proper place, as well as the apple trees. It turns out that in this same space, invisibly, the cosmic fluid of each apple was constantly passing through like a *simple substance* (LEIBNIZ, [1714] (2009)), unified, unique, and, in the set of apples, would be *in connection* with them the apple trees.

Like a “fluid” or a “coagulated light”, the perceptual image of the apples is eternalized in Tuczek’s perceptual consciousness. Could it be the action of the ether in the form of representing the apple in Tuczek's mind? It's a possibility.

If the ether propagates with light waves, then the medium is purely a reflection of this phenomenon. The apple absorbs the etheric field of its environment (the trees) and, thus, can project itself into any situation, being or phenomenon. The primary issue in this case is the “phenomenon”. Tuczek's phenomenon of “seeing” the apples for hours on end for a long period of time, ended up bringing, in his mind, the coagulated image of the apple's ether in the immanence of the *lived space*

² SANTOS, C. C. C. . O nada objetal. **Boletim de Conjuntura (BOCA)**, Boa Vista, vol. 11, no. 31, p. 64–75, 2022. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6635944. Available at: <https://revista.ioles.com.br/boca/index.php/revista/article/view/652>. Accessed on: 21 Aug. 2024.

of relationship. From this perspective, space would be the condensed accumulation of beings of all types, both material and immaterial.

The sensory universe of our mind is so abstract that it can be *absorbed* by any corpuscle directed towards light. Jaspers (1979), for this case, called it “a memory of senses”. But, we can go deeper into this definition and say - “a mind-blowing memory”. In other words, the episodic and/or lived record of the apple event was as if “eternalized” in its *episodic memory* (Tulving), or perhaps because of his mundane everyday way of growing apples, or because of his affection and/or *affection* (Spinoza) towards this particular lived space.

The reappearance of apples happens “at night” when the streets are dimly lit, blocking space with the shadows of darkness. This phenomenon is optical because it is also psychological in the sense that the symptoms of apples are caused by the luminous effect of street lamps that poorly illuminated the railways. Again, it is the effect of *luminescence* of vibrating waves of light the primary cause of the prototype and/or ghostly image of the apples. It is also quite certain that the relationship between the human mind and space produces a “ghost”, in this case, “optical”.

The low light of the *quite* leads to *little vibration* of luminous corpuscles; which also consequently entails the coagulation of the ethers of the representational image of the apples, condensing into a single time interval the memory and/or memory of the space lived in the apple tree. Not just in the unconscious, but in the *pure memory* (Bergson), this image remained there for a long time along with its lasting time when the event was taking place. It's really incredible how the mind is a mimesis of reality, in this case, physical reality. The psychic ended up mirroring the physical.

The more we look at the space around us or the environment, it is as if the mind brings within itself, in the deepest interior of itself, that *coagulated image of space as well as time*. It is as if the etheric field of the lived and/or experienced space, that is, the extremely concrete reality, *donate* some etheric particles of themselves in the transpassion to the psychic environment and also donate organically - the image of the ghost. Perhaps this is why famous painters like Michelangelo or Van Gogh liked to paint the nature of things because they knew much more than most that “art imitates life”.

The same could be said of this example. The psychic *imitates and/or represents* life, in the expensive use of the terms “imitate” and “represent”. In the case of marked psychopathologies, the individual naturally rich in visual and/or spatial imagination may *revive* in a very recurrent way the re-enactment of lived spaces or even their “resurrection”. In this specific case, they are usually negative and/or dark memory images of one or more possibly traumatic experiences.

The unconscious ether “likes” this type of situation when the individual has a certain obsessive way of always being focused on situations and spaces experienced. In an even more

important case, in schizophrenia, the individual can almost absolutely live the “imaginative space” much more than the “lived space”. In both, the etherealization of space, whether luminous or not, will always be present.

Case 02

From Johannes Mueller's self-observations on fantastic phenomena of vision we present the following excerpt: Sleepless nights became shorter when I could, so to speak, *walk awake among the very creatures of my eyes*. When I want to observe these bright images, I look into the darkness of the visual field with my eyes closed, completely at rest; with a feeling of relaxation and maximum tranquility in the orbicularis muscles, I immerse myself entirely in the sensitive rest of the eyes or in the darkness of my visual field. I push away all thoughts, all judgment... If, at first, the dark visual field is still rich in particular luminous points, in mists, in colors that change and transform, limited images of varied objects soon appear in their place, at first shining palely, then more distinctly. There is no doubt that they really shine and are often colorful. They move, they change, they often appear right at the edge of the visual field with a vividness and clarity of image like we have never seen anything so clear in images of the visual field. At the slightest movement of the eye they generally disappear; also reflection drives them away immediately. Known figures are rare, in general; They are singular figures, men, animals that I have never seen, *illuminated spaces I've never been to...* Not just at night, at any time of the day I am capable of these phenomena. I spent many hours resting, far from sleep, observing these phenomena with my eyes closed. Many times I just need to sit down, close my eyes, abstract myself from everything, these images involuntarily appear that have become friends with me since my early youth... *Often, the bright image appears in the dark visual field; Often the darkness of the visual field, before particular images appear, is gradually illuminated into a kind of pale inner daylight..* Soon after, the images appear. As curious as the appearance of the luminous images, since I have observed these phenomena, the progressive luminosity of the visual field has been for me, as I see daylight emerging within it little by little with my eyes closed and I see walking during the day, with my eyes closed, luminous figures as a product of the life of meaning itself; and all this in a vigil state, far from any superstition, from all fanaticism, with serene reflection, is something strangely wonderful for the observer... *I can distinguish exactly when the ghost lights up.* I sit for a long time with my eyes closed, everything I want to imagine is pure representation, a limitation imagined in the dark visual field. It does not light up, it does not move organically in the visual field; *Suddenly, however, the moment of sympathy arises between the fantastic and the nerve of light;* Instantly the figures are there shining without any stimulus from representation. The phenomenon is completely sudden. It is never first imagined, represented, and then made brilliant. I don't see what I want to see, I can only accept what, without any stimulus, I should see *shining*. The short-sighted objection that these are only represented phenomena, such as dreams, or, as they say, imagined phenomena, naturally falls apart of itself. *I can spend hours imagining it, but if there is no disposition for the luminous phenomenon, the previous representations will never be vivid..* And behold, suddenly, against my will, without any recognized association, *something appears shining that was not represented before.* But this phenomenon that I am capable of experiencing in a vigil state is a subjective visual phenomenon as certain as the stars that can be seen if you hit your head (JASPERS, 1979, p. 86-87, my emphasis).

As said, this is another real example of a very rich and complex case. When reading the episodic account, the reader immediately notices Mueller's mastery in describing in a fantastic and very detailed way the detail of intuitive-imaginative optical appearances. With a brilliant memory, he manages to describe, in a very profound way, even the immanence of the state of his ghostly appearance. Again, in this case too, it is the vibration of the ether particles of the waves and/or light currents that causes a clotted optical image of the luminous ether stuck in your visual imagination. Not that the eye actually "imagines" it, but it's almost that. When Mueller says - "walking awake among the very creatures of my eyes" reveals to us the immense penetrative power of the "nerves of light" that, as it passes through your dark visual field, illuminating it, causes the immanence of strange shapes to be projected; All because of its super sensitive sensitivity to lights.

The "nerves of light" in a state of formation would be the "very creatures of my eyes". For Mueller, these "creatures" and/or "ghosts" emerge from space out of nowhere. He says "figures" he had never seen, much less experienced. Unlike the previous case of lived space, here, the metaphysical fabric of space is formed not with eyes open "as I see the apples being picked and then reflected in the dimly lit railways", but with eyes closed when he says - "for I see the brightness of day appear within it little by little with my eyes closed and I see luminous figures walking around during the day, with their eyes closed, as a product of the life of meaning itself." In this particular case, there is an absolute and even eternal introspection of the lived space, as Mueller's eyes are closed and, according to him, within this dark visual field, *are born* and *are reborn* appearing luminous forms or figures that come and go, come and go; as if even with his eyes closed he saw the brightness of a simple day.

This specific case happens to human beings who lack good vision (especially those with myopia and/or retinal detachment). Because the visual field is now very dark, these individuals start to see only the recurrence of light sources entering and leaving their eyes; as if it were a dark plate of glass with lights shining all the time. In Mueller's case, as with any individual, he just had his eyes closed and the phenomenon occurred. It also turns out that Mueller himself certainly had a very pronounced sensitivity to light, therefore, the lens of his retina would almost perfectly reflect all the masterful organicity of the luminous corpuscles. Because, as optics well knows, not only the mind, but the organicity of the human eye was made to mirror and/or reflect the image of the world and to reach the mind in form, color, substance and light.

And Mueller goes on to describe - "*Suddenly, however, the moment of sympathy arises between the fantastic and the nerve of light; are instantly leaf shining the figures without any stimulus of representation*". In this case, the snapshot of the image would abruptly be the instantaneity of light. Interesting how he uses the term "nerve of light" as if the light we know itself carries a "nerve" in its organic form, just like an optic nerve for our eye. And Mueller emphasizes -

“the sympathy between the fantastic and the nerve of light”. The entire phenomenon that involves light is of a “fantastic” order simply because light, like the ether, penetrates everything.

However, the question that can be asked here is - “why does Mueller have a certain *predisposition* to ‘see’ these creatures within themselves, that is, in their visual field?” Could this be a creation of his fantastic mind or some kind of psychopathology? We must remember that not only problems and/or visual changes resulting from some disease can trigger the appearance of phenomena like these, but, even in the present act of the eye “creating” these luminous creatures, it is still the mind (perceptual consciousness) its originating cause.

According to Jaspers (1979), this case can be described as when some people (normally young or barely adult) have a very important and present visual-perceptual memory that can psychically and optically transpose the image of the shape of a flower garden on the paper when the sees into the fabric of space. As he himself describes: “if eidetic people are presented with images of flowers, fruits or any other object on a sheet of gray paper, they can see, after removing the images, the object again with all its particularities, perhaps in front of or behind the paper” (JASPERS, 1979, p. 87). The phenomenon-situation is similar to when we look closely at a physical figure in space (like a simple pencil) and seconds later, when returning the visual field to the center of the computer, the pencil clearly reappears right in front of the device. According to Jaspers, these individuals are beings with a very strong eidetic nature, which means that, in the case of their visuo-perceptive consciousness, they *absorb* that which is essential during the heat of things. Beings like this have a great imagination and/or visual memory and can memorize situations and/or places very precisely. In this case, let us remember Goethe and his autobiography where he even described what the smell of flowers were like in the spring of his youth.

In this sense, all the voltaic combustion of the ethers both within Mueller's thought and in his recurrence of the luminous crystals of the light nerves of his visual field attest to the fact that all this “spatialization” of the luminous corpuscles within the etheric field of its invisible illuminating particles cause the formation of those “luminous creatures”; and the proliferation of lights can come both from the environment (that is, the space lived in the concreteness of the world) and from the space lived inside the mind as a form of representation. Everything will depend a lot on contact with previous experiences, as well as and above all, the singular organicity of the organic part of each individual's psyche.

In view of this, we remember that because it is “light”, that is, something that illuminates everything, both inside and outside any type of substance (material and/or immaterial), that is, both inside and outside the mind, the “light” for being one of the few things that is something “unfathomable”, for permeating any field, any surface, abstract or concrete, leads us to believe that

the problem, in this case, of the etherization of light itself could become a completely without a solution, or rather, indecipherable.

In this example case, Mueller like any other individual (including all beings, forms or artifacts), is at all times subject to, or rather, *being-absorbed* in an immeasurable and unfathomable way by the light of the world, by the light of lived space. Not that light or ether are the primary causes of a triggering of a “sick” mind, but the primary question perhaps (and this is the central question of our essay), is - “how to escape the world if with open eyes I Am I him and with my eyes closed too?”

Perhaps, even more, the problem is not in the cosmic creation of this space lived by a God or a Creator, but the real problem perhaps lies in the fact of the capacity of the human psychic nature to reflect *at the same time* all phenomena and, from the eye that gives the form and the mind that reflects the ocular image, produce an infinite immensity of relationships like how many celestial bodies there would be in the sky.

Final considerations

Perhaps, given what has been presented here very briefly on a very dense and profound topic, we can conclude by saying that there is a lot to understand regarding psychic phenomena and their possible psychopathologies with regard to the *lived space*. Little is said about this here in Brazil. Perhaps, following an almost Heideggerian thought, a good part of mental changes (which fall into a possible psychopathology) originate from *relationship between the living being and the living being in the lived space*. In other words, Minkowski was completely correct! Therefore, we emphasize once again that *it is not* the lived space causes a diversity of psychoses or neuroses, but, on the contrary, *is the meaning* that is made of the relationship with this lived space, which would lead to a kind of “psychosemantics of space”.

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